

A first short post inspired by Vojtech Kolman's book "On Bad Infinity" or
on neo-"materialism" and therefore finiteness of every abstraction

The problem of infinity or limitlessness lies in the fact that when we think about real objects and when we count their amount, our abstraction does not only leave out particular characteristics of those real objects (molecules, bricks, cars, etc.), but it also leaves out specific reasons why there is always only a limited amount of those objects in reality. On the planet Earth there isn't enough material for us to be able to create an unlimited quantity of bricks and we don't have unlimited time, nor unlimited speed of their manufacturing. On top of that, we don't have enough space to store an unlimited quantity of bricks. Should we think about bricks in an abstract manner, we can imagine them in an amount that corresponds for instance with the weight of the Milky Way, and therefore we are overcoming the limitations of reality. Let's notice that the limitation of the number of real objects is always a limitation outer; the reason behind finiteness is not inner.

For the purpose of mathematics, we abstract away from all characteristics of real objects, in order to create a row of abstract objects called numbers that represent real objects (for simplicity let's stick to natural numbers: 1, 2, 3, etc.). As mentioned above, it appears that this abstraction also removed any concrete limitations to the amount of real objects. That's why it appears that when it comes to abstract objects called numbers, we can keep increasing them without limits and so they can grow all the way till infinity. Nevertheless, any borders of values of numbers disappear only seemingly, because just as all concrete types of objects merged into one abstract type of objects (numbers), all real borders merged into one border of abstraction. However, this border does not seem to exist within the abstract world. This is not entirely true, but for now let's not examine borders inside the abstract world. Let's just use the above-mentioned piece of information that the limitation is outer, and our search will head in that direction. Surprisingly we will not find limitations of abstraction in the world of abstraction, but in reality. Abstraction is always submerged in the real world because it is carried out by a material implementer. When it comes to this implementer, multiple borders of amounts of real objects merged into one type of border – real borders, determined by the "enabler" of the abstraction, whether it is a human, a computer or anything else.

No implementer of abstraction has the luxury of unlimited speed of operations with abstract objects, nor of unlimited time to complete an infinite row, nor of infinite memory capacity to retain all abstract objects (for instance numbers). Nature simply does not allow infinity to happen in any form, so when we try to use abstraction to eliminate all borders of a number of concrete objects in reality, it vengefully blocks us with physical limitations common amongst all who use abstraction. Evidently, abstraction manifest itself as a material process in a material bearer of information.

An algorithm that seemingly establishes infinity (for example in the case of natural numbers "always add 1") is only an unattainable wish, should we intend to take it all the way to an endless end. Infinity is therefore not an object that belongs to any set (for instance the set of natural numbers) or anywhere else. It is a mere chimera, even in the kingdom of abstraction. Infinity is just an illusion, which tells us that we cannot see any farther and that our ability to abstract ends here. Hic sunt leones.

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PS: To keep this post short as promised, a post no2 will examine why finiteness is caused by "interaction" of outer and inner causality.